

The fundamental context of SEL for early childhood student teachers in private higher education institutions

Yupawadee Promsatien¹, Ariyabhorn Kuroda¹, Suwadee Aerarunchot², Sungwean Pinagalang¹

¹Department of Curriculum and Instruction, Faculty of Education, Khon Kaen University, Khon Kaen, Thailand

²Department of Prosthodontic, Faculty of Dentistry, Khon Kaen University, Khon Kaen, Thailand

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ABSTRACT

This research examined the learning needs and the current social and emotional conditions of early childhood student teachers in private higher education institutions. The sample group responding to the questionnaire comprised 343 undergraduate students majoring in early childhood education. The target group for interviews included nine participants, which consisted of 3 deans, 3 department heads, and 3 lecturers. The research instruments consisted of a questionnaire on the state and needs of social and emotional learning (SEL) and an interview guide on the current social and emotional conditions of early childhood student teachers. The data were analyzed using percentage, mean, standard deviation, and content analysis. The findings revealed that the state of learning among pre-service teachers was at a low level, while their learning needs were high. Furthermore, the current conditions indicated that pre-service teachers require enhanced SEL opportunities. Activities fostering such learning should be designed, including group work, experiential learning, listening to others, and engaging in discussions.

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Corresponding Author:

Yupawadee Promsatien

Department of Curriculum and Instruction, Faculty of Education, Khon Kaen University

123 Mitrapharp Rd., Amphoe Muang Khon Kaen, Khon Kaen, Thailand

Email: pr.yupawadee@kkumail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, the world is changing rapidly, making the role of education increasingly important in providing a competitive advantage for countries. The development of the potential and capabilities of Thai people, equipping them with the skills, knowledge, abilities, and competencies that align with labor market demands, is crucial for improving the quality of life in Thailand. This will lead to a society with ethical values and help the country transition from being a middle-income nation to a developed one, preparing for global changes both now and in the future [1], [2]. Therefore, education is a key tool in national development and guiding the country through the changes that will occur in the future. As stated in the royal speech of His Majesty King Bhumibol Adulyadej [3], “education is a tool to develop knowledge, thinking, behavior, attitudes, values, and ethics of individuals, to ensure they become quality and effective citizens.” In the development of education, a key factor is the “teacher,” who transmits knowledge to learners and helps develop them to receive quality education and acquire the knowledge and abilities necessary to lead the country through change.

“Teachers” thus play a crucial role in driving the nation’s education system and developing students to possess the desired characteristics for a high-quality, modern society. Teachers are responsible for managing the learning process to help students reach their full potential. Therefore, teachers must have teaching skills focused on achieving educational outcomes, as well as possess ethics, moral values, language

communication skills, and adaptability to society. It can be said that teachers should have both hard skills and soft skills [4]. Hence, the production of high-quality teachers requires development in all areas, not just focusing on hard skills or professional competencies. Teachers need to be prepared in other aspects as well to be able to adapt to various situations that will arise in the future. Soft skills are crucial to supporting smooth operations, such as interpersonal relationships, leadership, emotional understanding and regulation, social awareness, time management, and self-management. Additionally, social and emotional learning (SEL) is an essential skill for teachers, as it is the ability to recognize and understand one's own thoughts, emotions, and feelings, as well as those of others. SEL consists of five components: self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, responsible decision-making, and relationship skills [5]–[7]. Global organizations like Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and UNESCO emphasize the promotion of SEL for students, teachers, and communities, particularly enhancing teachers' SEL, as it improves teaching and learning processes, leading to successful education outcomes that ultimately benefit students [8]–[10]. Teachers with social and emotional understanding can develop relationship skills, support and motivate students, design lessons that highlight students' strengths, find ways to foster intrinsic motivation, help students navigate conflicts, and promote collaboration among students, serving as role models for respectful communication [11]–[13].

The current issues related to teachers' SEL, as reflected in their behavior, have been observed in both public and private sector teachers. These issues include problems such as teacher attrition, teacher misconduct toward students, stress, family issues, financial difficulties, conflicts with colleagues and supervisors, among others. These problems can arise from a variety of factors. When these issues occur, some teachers are unable to manage or control their emotions, leading to emotional distress and stress. Over time, accumulated emotional strain can negatively impact students. A study by the University of Missouri in 2018 found that 93% of teachers who were surveyed and reported high levels of stress had students with lower academic performance and more aggressive behaviors [14]. Many educators believe that teacher stress directly affects the learning effectiveness and well-being of students. This is evident in the news shared across various social media feeds, where teachers continuously face accumulated stress and then take out their feelings on students, such as through inappropriate reprimands or even physical abuse, ranging from minor to severe cases [15], [16]. On the other hand, teachers who possess good SEL skills can create a positive environment, providing space for students to feel comfortable, understand their own and their students' emotions, and effectively manage their emotions. This, in turn, positively impacts the students' learning and their social and emotional adjustment.

Although SEL are important for teachers, there is still a lack of serious promotion and support from the government and higher education institutions. This leaves student teachers lacking in SEL skills because they are not trained. Suppose higher education institutions want to develop SEL in the classroom. In that case, educators can develop these skills by providing opportunities for learners to practice through interactive learning activities at the school. Such as group work, discussions, and project-based learning, which allow for communication between each other, learners can review themselves, understand themselves, and understand their friends. Also, discussions occur to solve problems together, with teachers using a learner-centered teaching process and allowing learners to participate in designing the learning process. Therefore, prioritizing SEL in teacher preparation will improve the quality of education management. When pre-service teachers are adequately prepared, they will be better equipped with SEL skills, enabling them to perform their teaching profession more effectively in the future [17], [18].

2. METHOD

2.1. Population and target group

The population consisted of undergraduate students majoring in early childhood education who were studying at private higher education institutions, totaling 3,141 students in Thailand [19]. The sample group consisted of 343 undergraduate students majoring in early childhood education from private higher education institutions in Thailand. This sample size was determined using the pre-calculated table by Krejcie and Morgan [20]. The researcher applied a two-stage cluster sampling method based on the geographical location of 17 institutions. Afterward, quota sampling was used to select participants based on the required number from each of the 17 institutions.

The target group consisted of deans, department heads, and lecturers, totaling nine individuals from private higher education institutions in Thailand. They were selected through purposive sampling. It consisted of 3 deans, 3 department heads with at least 5 years of experience in their respective positions, and 3 lecturers with at least 5 years of teaching experience in private higher education institutions.

2.2. Research instruments

The research instruments consisted of questionnaires and interview forms, which were quality-checked by five experts with expertise in SEL, curriculum and instruction, measurement and evaluation, and psychology. The expert-reviewed questionnaire was found to have an item-objective congruence (IOC) value that passed all criteria, with an IOC value of 0.60 or higher. First, a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire on the current state and needs of SEL, covering five aspects with a total of 45 items, divided into three parts. Part 1, general information about the respondents, including questions about gender, age, university/college, and the level of the program they are studying. These questions are multiple-choice, totaling 5 items. Part 2, the current state of SEL, using a 5-point Likert scale. Participants were asked to rate their opinions on statements related to issues in SEL. The scale is as: 1=very low, 2=quite low, 3=moderate, 4=quite high, 5=high. This section includes 20 items across five aspects. Part 3, the needs for SEL, using a 5-point Likert scale. Participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement, perception, or practice with the provided statements, with the following scale: 1=very low, 2=quite low, 3=moderate, 4=quite high, and 5=high. This section covers 5 aspects, with a total of 20 items. Secondly, an interview with deans, department heads, and lecturers regarding the current state of SEL for pre-service teachers. This is a semi-structured interview consisting of open-ended questions related to the current state of SEL for pre-service teachers, with a total of five questions.

2.3. Data collection

2.3.1. Questionnaire data collection

The researcher followed these steps to collect questionnaire data from students: i) prepared an official letter to request cooperation for data collection in this research. The letter was issued by the Faculty of Education, Khon Kaen University, and addressed to the deans of the Faculty of Education at all 17 universities; ii) contacted the department heads or faculty members responsible for the target groups to request permission to explain the research project details and the data collection process; iii) scheduled a session to provide details about the research project, explain data protection measures, obtain informed consent from volunteer participants, and guide them on how to complete the online questionnaire using Google Forms. The explanation session was conducted online via Zoom and lasted 20 minutes; and iv) sent the Google Form, accessible via a QR code, to the faculty members responsible for the target groups. These faculty members facilitated data collection from the student volunteers. Once participants completed and submitted the online questionnaire, the data were considered successfully collected.

2.3.2. Interview data collection

The researcher followed these steps to collect interview data from deans, department heads, and lecturers: i) prepared an official letter to request cooperation for data collection in this research. The letter was issued by the Faculty of Education, Khon Kaen University, and addressed to the respective organizations of the volunteer participants; ii) coordinated with the participants' organizations to obtain their contact information; iii) contacted the participants to request permission to introduce the research project, explain data protection measures, obtain informed consent, and outline the interview process. The explanation session was conducted online via Zoom and lasted 20 minutes; iv) interested participants were instructed to contact the researcher using the provided contact information. Once participants confirmed their willingness to join the study, the researcher scheduled an interview and obtained formal consent; and v) interviews were conducted onsite using a semi-structured interview format. Each interview lasted approximately 40 minutes and took place in a meeting room or the participant's office during their convenient working hours.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results on the SEL conditions and needs of early childhood student teachers

3.1.1. Part 1: analysis of the respondents' background information

The researcher conducted a survey study using a questionnaire distributed to early childhood student teachers. The details are presented in Table 1. According to the table, the majority of respondents are female, comprising 312 individuals or 90.96%. The age group 21-25 years accounts for 136 individuals or 39.66%. Most respondents are in their first year of study, with 145 individuals, representing 42.27%. In terms of employment status, 208 individuals or 60.64%, are currently unemployed. Regarding marital status, 252 individuals or 73.47% are single. Additionally, 267 individuals or 77.84%, have completed education below the bachelor's degree level.

Table 1. Background information of early childhood student teachers

Variable	Background information	Number (N=343)	Percentage
Gender	Male	31	9.04
	Female	312	90.96
Age	18-20 years	125	36.44
	21-25 years	136	39.66
	26-30 years	54	15.74
	30 years or older	28	8.16
Year of study	Year 1	145	42.27
	Year 2	36	10.50
	Year 3	45	13.12
	Year 4	117	34.11
Employment status	Employed	135	39.36
	Unemployed	208	60.64
Marital status	Single	252	73.47
	Married	89	25.95
	Divorced	2	0.58
Highest level of education prior to enrollment	Below a bachelor's degree	267	77.84
	Bachelor's degree	76	22.16

3.1.2. Part 2: SEL conditions

The researcher employed a survey study approach, administering a questionnaire to early childhood student teachers. Table 2 displays the relevant details. The table shows that the overall SEL conditions of early childhood student teachers are rated as low ($M=2.46$). The perceptions in each aspect are as: aspect 1, self-awareness, is rated as moderate ($M=2.71$); aspect 2, self-management, is rated as low; aspect 3, social awareness, is rated as low ($M=2.46$); aspect 4, responsible decision-making, is rated as low ($M=2.48$); and aspect 5, relationship skills, is rated as moderate ($M=2.50$).

Table 2. Early childhood student teachers' perceptions of SEL conditions

Aspects	SEL conditions	M	S.D.	Perception level
1	Self-awareness	2.71	0.91	Moderate
2	Self-management	2.16	0.92	Low
3	Social awareness	2.46	0.88	Low
4	Responsible decision-making	2.48	0.86	Low
5	Relationship skills	2.50	0.91	Moderate
	Overall	2.46	0.89	Low

(Criteria for the level of need: $M=1.00-2.49$ =low, $2.50-3.49$ =moderate, $3.50-4.49$ =high, $4.50-5.00$ =very high)

3.1.3. Part 3: need for the development of SEL

The researcher conducted a survey study using a questionnaire administered to early childhood student teachers. The information is outlined in Table 3. Based on the table, the developmental needs in SEL among early childhood student teachers are generally at a high level, with an average score of 4.45. The levels of need for each aspect are as: self-awareness is rated at a high level ($M=3.82$); self-management is rated at the very high level ($M=4.59$); social awareness is rated at the very high level ($M=4.51$); responsible decision-making is rated at the very high level ($M=4.66$); and relationship skills are also rated at the very high level ($M=4.61$).

Table 3. Developmental needs in SEL among early childhood student teachers

Aspects	Developmental needs in SEL	M	S.D.	Level of need
1	Self-awareness	3.82	0.88	High
2	Self-management	4.59	0.86	Very high
3	Social awareness	4.54	0.75	Very high
4	Responsible decision-making	4.66	0.85	Very high
5	Relationship skills	4.67	0.83	Very high
	Overall	4.45	0.83	High

(Criteria for the level of need: $M=1.00-2.49$ =low, $2.50-3.49$ =moderate, $3.50-4.49$ =high, $4.50-5.00$ =very high)

3.2. Results on the current SEL conditions of early childhood student teachers

To explore the current SEL conditions of early childhood student teachers, the researcher employed interviews with nine participants, including deans, department heads, and lecturers. The interviews covered five key topics, which are open-ended questions. The findings are summarized as:

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- a. What are the general characteristics of SEL? The participants answered:

“For self-awareness, first- and second-year pre-service teachers demonstrate lower levels compared to those in higher years. Regarding self-management, issues with responsibility for assigned tasks were observed. In terms of social awareness, students generally understand their roles, show social awareness, and maintain acceptance within their close peer groups. For responsible decision-making, emotional decision-making often overshadows reasoning, and students lack effective problem-solving skills. For relationship skills, students predominantly socialize within their familiar peer groups.”

- b. Are there SEL conditions that affect teaching and learning? How are they? The participants answered:

“During the teaching, there were some slightly dissatisfied facial expressions, such as when the teacher divided into groups with friends who were not close, which made them dissatisfied, but they were able to control their emotions, accept it, and work in groups as usual. This may come from the diversity of experiences and age groups, which sometimes causes students to become stressed from studying with friends who have more experience, causing them to not dare to talk or exchange opinions.”

- c. What should the context, environment, and methods be for promoting SEL? The participants answered:

“The context that is conducive to promoting emotional and social learning of student teachers should be a context where students are happy, have freedom, can learn from what they want and can apply the knowledge they have gained further. The learning method should be organized both in groups and individually so that students can learn completely. Activities should be organized that allow students to learn from themselves and others, socialize, listen to opinions, and dare to express themselves.”

- d. What are the approaches for enhancing SEL? The participants answered:

“Activities should be designed to be diverse according to students’ interests, allowing them to express themselves more, should encourage absorption through classroom activities. Teachers need to understand and address learners’ needs while showing care and attention to them. Because expressing themselves will reveal clearer emotional and social behaviors, which will help them correct deficiencies caused by emotional states.”

- e. Is the SEL of early childhood teacher-students important for their future as teachers? How? The participants answered:

“SEL is crucial for instilling the spirit of teaching, preparing pre-service teachers for their future roles. It supports their professional work, adaptation, and social integration as educators. Without strong SEL, teachers may struggle in their profession and negatively impact their students.”

3.3. Discussion

From the study of the fundamental context of SEL for early childhood student teachers in private higher education institutions, the researcher identifies the following points for discussion.

3.3.1. The importance of clear policies on SEL enhancement the findings emphasize the need for increased attention to SEL in government education policies

Current policies predominantly focus on cognitive knowledge and technical skills, with limited emphasis on the affective domain, particularly SEL for pre-service teachers. This approach contrasts with international practices, where greater emphasis is placed on the integration of SEL as an essential component of teacher preparation programs. Promoting SEL among pre-service teachers is vital, as it not only fosters these competencies in students [18], [21], but also supports teachers in effectively managing their professional responsibilities. These responsibilities include teaching, administrative tasks, and interactions with students, parents, and colleagues, all of which benefit from emotional intelligence and social skills. Without proper training in these areas, teachers may struggle to manage their emotional well-being, which can negatively impact their performance and relationships within the school environment. Thus, SEL enables teachers to understand their roles, empathize with students, and address challenges effectively. This aligns

with the study [22], which investigated teachers' attitudes toward the development of social and emotional skills in primary schools in Greece. The study found that many teachers lacked essential social and emotional skills that they should instill in their students, such as empathy and basic emotional regulation, including emotions like happiness, sadness, fear, and anger. Additionally, the study highlighted the significant influence of feelings and self-esteem, noting that these factors can positively or negatively impact students.

3.3.2. The significance of fostering SEL for pre-service teachers, which teacher training institutions should prioritize due to its necessity for cultivating competent future educators

a. Self-awareness

Newly enrolled pre-service teachers often struggle to adjust, which may stem from the transition to a higher level of education, differences in learning from their previous secondary school experiences, and various environmental factors such as social settings, family background, peer relationships, age, and diverse experiences [23]–[25]. These factors may affect their ability to understand and recognize themselves. This finding aligns with the study by Alexander and Vermette [26], which identified academic performance, school size, and parental status as predictive factors influencing SEL. Teacher preparation programs should prioritize the needs of newly enrolled pre-service teachers, as insufficient self-awareness may negatively impact their learning process. Institutions should implement strategies and design activities that enable pre-service teachers to practice self-awareness continuously. Suggested activities include mindfulness meditation, breath awareness, and self-reflection exercises, ensuring autonomy and avoiding coercion to encourage genuine self-recognition. Additionally, providing opportunities for pre-service teachers to engage with real-world scenarios in schools and classrooms will allow them to observe and experience the actual roles of a teacher. This hands-on experience is instrumental in helping them understand the broader context and responsibilities of the teaching profession.

b. Self-management

Pre-service teachers tend to rely more on emotions than on reasoning and lack strategies or methods for managing their emotions. This may be due to classroom activities not providing opportunities for pre-service teachers to learn or practice how to cope with emotions and feelings when faced with different situations, resulting in a lack of emotional control. This can negatively affect both themselves and others, as teaching requires interaction with students, parents, and colleagues. Therefore, self-management, including emotional regulation and appropriate responses to various situations, is crucial for pre-service teachers to reduce problems arising from different circumstances, resolve issues smoothly, and build trust with students and parents [27]. Consequently, teacher education programs should incorporate activities that promote self-management, offering pre-service teachers the opportunity to face emotional challenges, apply problem-solving skills, and practice emotional regulation in different scenarios. This is in line with research by Sittichai and Smith [28] which states that problem-solving skills enable individuals to find solutions that lead to goals independently, effectively meeting their needs and increasing self-awareness. Therefore, activities should include role-playing, problem-solving scenarios, and deep listening exercises.

c. Social awareness

Pre-service teachers show care and consideration for the emotions and feelings of others, particularly when the individual is someone they are close to. This skill is essential for teachers, as they need to understand the differences in the thoughts, feelings, and emotions of their students in order to assist in their development and problem-solving. Furthermore, when teachers have social awareness, they can use their knowledge to contribute to the development of society, communities, and the nation. Therefore, to enhance social awareness in pre-service teachers, teacher education institutions should understand the context, family background, and social environment of the pre-service teachers. They should also listen to their opinions without judgment and provide opportunities for them to encounter new social settings [29]. For example, organizing group activities—starting with smaller groups and gradually expanding to larger ones—will allow pre-service teachers to get to know each other more closely, which can help foster stronger friendships among them.

d. Responsible decision-making

Pre-service teachers tend to rely on emotions before reasoning, often making decisions without carefully considering the consequences, which sometimes leads to mistakes [30]. Decision-making with responsibility is crucial for the teaching profession because the behaviors and outcomes of a teacher's decisions are closely observed by society. Teachers serve as role models for students and society, and students often emulate their behavior, whether it is positive or negative. Therefore, a teacher's decision-making abilities are influenced by social norms. Teachers must consider the impact of their decisions, both on themselves and on society. To enhance decision-making with responsibility in pre-service teachers, teacher education institutions should design activities that require pre-service teachers to face problems independently. Additionally, clear rules and guidelines should be established at both the institutional and classroom levels, which pre-service teachers must follow to promote responsible decision-making.

e. Relationship skills

Pre-service teachers tend to form relationships with individuals they are close to and trust. Factors such as age, education, social context, and the surrounding environment may influence relationship-building, which is essential for teachers. Teachers must regularly interact with students, parents, and colleagues, and maintaining good relationships helps facilitate smooth teaching, work, student development, and problem-solving. Fostering an understanding of relationships through concepts related to SEL and integration helps prevent and resolve issues that may arise in the workplace [31]. This, in turn, enables individuals to perform better in a suitable environment, gaining respect and trust from students, trust from parents, and support from colleagues. Therefore, teacher education institutions should pay more attention to this aspect by designing activities or programs that promote relationship-building for pre-service teachers [32]. These activities may start small within the classroom and expand to the department, faculty, and ultimately the entire institution.

3.3.3. Promoting SEL in the classroom integrating SEL into the curriculum and designing activities that support students' social and emotional development is crucial [33]

Teacher education institutions have tended to place less emphasis on fostering SEL for pre-service teachers, likely due to educational policies that prioritize knowledge and skill development. Consequently, teaching methods often overlook the psychological aspects of training. However, merely possessing knowledge and skills is insufficient for ensuring that pre-service teachers succeed in their careers. The evolving social landscape and global changes have impacted societal conditions, highlighting the necessity of addressing all aspects of development. Therefore, providing equal attention to emotional, social, and cognitive growth will enhance pre-service teachers' chances of leading successful and fulfilling careers. Recent reports of teachers resigning due to personal issues, workplace challenges, or interpersonal conflicts, as well as instances of teachers harming students, underscore the importance of SEL. These events suggest that teachers may lack the ability to understand, regulate, and manage their emotions, resolve conflicts, and interact effectively within society [34]. Therefore, teaching methods that promote psychological development play a crucial role in fostering SEL [35]. Classroom activities might include scenario-based exercises derived from real-life experiences, allowing pre-service teachers to practice recognizing thoughts and emotions, as well as engaging in group activities to develop social skills [36].

3.3.4. Guidelines for developing SEL of student teachers

The research results show the current needs and SEL conditions of student teachers that are expected to be urgently addressed for continuous implementation. The policy setting by the administrators should see the importance and set clear regulations for implementation. The budget should be allocated to create learning facilities both outside the classroom and in the classroom, such as: a place to relax, an internet to access information easily, a classroom that is conducive to learning, and also promotes the insertion of content, sets continuous activities every week and includes it in the curriculum of the subject. During the teaching and learning activities, teachers should allow students to learn by themselves as much as possible, give importance to flexibility in terms of time and place, prepare sufficient media and equipment, and observe students' gestures, facial expressions, and eyes that show the need for help. Also, immediately provide assistance and advice, leaving a gap of appropriate care and support, without being too intrusive, because it will make the learner feel uncomfortable, and not be themselves.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the study of the fundamental context for SEL for early childhood student teachers at private higher education institutions, the researcher concluded: emotional and social learning management is important for student teachers to become good teachers in the future. Learning in all five dimensions, namely self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, responsible decision-making, and relationship building, still needs to be promoted and supported more. Thai education still places little importance on this issue. There are no clear policies or promotion guidelines, causing teacher training institutions to not see their importance. Additionally, there is no concrete classroom learning management system. Although emotional and social learning is essential for adaptive living, work, and social life.

Therefore, importance should be given to this issue from childhood to adulthood by setting educational policies at all levels, setting specific curricula, organizing volunteer activities both inside and outside the school every year, and designing learning management that is suitable for learning. For researchers interested in this issue, there should be further research on developing learning management models that specifically promote emotional and social learning. Also, the long-term results should be studied with student teachers who have used this emotional and social learning model to track the direct effects on student teachers and the indirect effects on the students they teach.

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Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Yupawadee Promsatiem	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓
Ariyabhorn Kuroda	✓	✓		✓		✓			✓	✓		✓		✓
Suwadee Aerarunchot				✓		✓	✓			✓	✓		✓	✓
Sungwean Pinagalang			✓			✓		✓		✓	✓			

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

INFORMED CONSENT

We have obtained informed consent from all individuals included in this study.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This article is part of a doctoral thesis titled “Instructional Model to Enhance Social and Emotional Learning for early childhood student Teachers in Private Higher Education Institutions.” This research has been approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee of Khon Kaen University (Approval No.: HE663383; IRB00012791; and FWA00003418).

DATA AVAILABILITY

This research is a part of the doctoral study at Khon Kaen University. The library database of Khon Kaen University can be accessed.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Yupawadee Promsatien is a student doctoral degree for the Department of Curriculum and Instruction, Faculty of Education, Khon Kaen University in Thailand. She is an assistant professor of curriculum and instruction. She has been working for the Department of Early Childhood Education, Faculty of Education, Pitchayabundit College. Her research focuses on social and emotional learning, early childhood education. She can be contacted at email: pr.yupawadee@kkumail.com.

Ariyabhorn Kuroda is an assistant professor of curriculum and instruction. She has been working for Department of Curriculum and Instruction, Faculty of Education, Khon Kaen University in Thailand. Her research focuses on social and emotional learning, contemplative education, and professional development. She can be contacted at email: kurodaariyabhorn@gmail.com.

Suwadee Aerarunchot is an associate professor of dentistry and she has a doctorate degree in curriculum and instruction. She has been working for Department of Prosthodontic, Faculty of Dentistry, Khon Kaen University in Thailand. Her research focuses on contemplative education and developments in prosthetic dentistry. She can be contacted at email: asuwadee@kku.ac.th.

Sungwean Pinagalang has been working for Department of Curriculum and Instruction, Faculty of Education, Khon Kaen University in Thailand. His research focuses on mathematics studies and professional development. He can be contacted at email: sunpin@kku.ac.th.